

Data Management Plan Interoperability Framework

Technical Implementation Guide for Service Integration

Factsheet for: Software Engineers and Service Operators implementing DMP interoperability

What is the DMP-IF?

The Data Management Plan Interoperability Framework (DMP-IF) is a standardised common REST API and data model for exchanging machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) between research services.

Core Capabilities:

- Retrieve DMPs from any compliant service via REST API
- Search and filter DMPs by project, institution, or dataset criteria
- Create and update DMPs programmatically from external systems
- Sync metadata bidirectionally between repositories and DMP platforms

Architecture

DMP-IF defines three standardised layers that services implement independently:

- DMP Common Standard for maDMPs:** Establishes a structured, machine-actionable model for DMPs, ensuring interoperability across institutions, repositories, and research infrastructures. It enables automated updates, validation, and alignment with FAIR principles.
- OSTrails Application Profile:** Extends the DCS by incorporating domain-specific metadata, controlled vocabularies, enhancing machine-readability, policy compliance, and integration with diverse research workflows.
- Common maDMP API:** Provides a standardised interface for real-time data exchange, enabling automated ingestion from repositories, bidirectional integration with research data systems, and connections to SKGs for enriched metadata and discoverability, as well as for assessment (to provide better guidance).

Implementation:

In **Yellow** - DMP platforms operate with their own internal data models and components, e.g. user interface, document generation, custom integrations.

In **Purple** - The DMP-IF provides a mapping layer that translates each platform's internal representation to the Common Data Model, which is then accessible via the Common API.

The Outcome: Platforms maintain independence while achieving interoperability.

Technical Specifications

1. Data Model & Schema

Format: JSON conforming to RDA DMP Common Standard + OSTRails extensions

2. REST API Endpoints

Method	Endpoint	Description
GET	/dmps	List all accessible DMPs
GET	/dmps/{id}	Retrieve specific DMP
POST	/dmps	Create new DMP
PUT	/dmps/{id}	Update existing DMP

Query Parameters (GET /dmps)

- 🔗 page (integer): Page number for pagination
- 🔗 per_page (integer): Items per page (max 100)
- 🔗 project_id (string): Filter by project identifier
- 🔗 modified_since (ISO 8601): Filter by modification date

3. DMP Assessment & Compliance

DMP-IF integrates with the OSTRails DMP Evaluation Service API to assess DMPs for FAIRness, openness, policy compliance, and RDM community best practices.

API Integration:

<https://github.com/ostrails/dmp-evaluation-service>

Services can submit maDMPs for automated scoring and receive structured assessment results via REST API.

Enabling EOSC Data Management Federation

DMP-IF implements the federation layer for EOSC data management infrastructure. The federation emerges as EOSC services adopt DMP-IF for interoperable data management.

Federation Capabilities:

- 🔗 Decentralised maDMP exchange across EOSC Nodes
- 🔗 Cross-node FAIR and policy compliance assessment
- 🔗 Metadata synchronisation without central registry
- 🔗 Unified researcher access to distributed data management

Contribution to EOSC

OSTRails enables federated FAIR data management across EOSC ecosystem by providing a blueprint for seamless tool integration, lifecycle-wide planning and assessment, and capacity-building through shared frameworks and pilots.

Current Implementations

The DMP-IF is designed with DMP Platforms (Argos / OpenCDMP, DAMAP, FAIR Wizard / DSW) but can be used by any service or tool capable of exchanging maDMPs. The IF does not prescribe internal organisation of services, e.g. their architecture or how they represent information internally.

Resources & Documentation

RDA DMP Common Standard:

<https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard>

Full API Specification:

<https://docs.ostrails.eu/en/latest/commons/dmp/madmp-api-specification.html>

JSON Schema:

<https://github.com/RDA-DMP-Common/RDA-DMP-Common-Standard/tree/v1.2/examples/JSON/JSON-schema/1.2>

OSTRails GitHub: <https://github.com/OSTRails>

Documentation: <https://docs.ostrails.eu/>

Training resources: <https://ostrails.eu/training>

About OSTRails

<https://ostrails.eu>

Support / Contact Us:

info-ostrails@openaire.eu

Supporting

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